

ONCE AGAIN ABOUT THAT TURAKURGAN SCIENTIST

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Annotation: *In this article, Ibrat's contribution to jurisprudence, the sacrifice of the nation, a great representative of literature, the poet's activity is revealed through historical sources and analysis of his works. The article also comments on the essence of Ibrat's article "Haq Soz" written in the "Selected Works" collection. A deep analysis of the poet's poem "Judge Killer". In addition, quotes from the comments of various literary scholars about Ibrat's contribution to jurisprudence were cited and their opinions were proved.*

Key words: *jurisprudence, legal activity, justice, society, democracy, mullah, imam, mosque, debt, reward, punishment, education, science.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье через исторические источники и анализ его произведений раскрывается вклад Ибрата в юриспруденцию, самопожертвование нации, великого представителя литературы, деятельность поэта. В статье также комментируется суть статьи Ибрата «“Истинное слова”», написанной в сборнике «Избранные произведения». Глубокий анализ стихотворения поэта «Судья-убийца». Кроме того, приводились цитаты из комментариев различных литературоведов о вкладе Ибрата в юриспруденцию и доказывались их мнения.*

Ключевые слова: *юриспруденция, юридическая деятельность, правосудие, общество, демократия, мулла, имам, мечеть, долг, вознаграждение, наказание, образование, наука.*

Аннотация: *Ushbu maqolada millat fidoiysi, adabiyotning yirik vakili Ibratning huquqshunoslikka qo'shgan hissasi, shoir faoliyatini tarixiy manbalardan*

hamda, o'z asarlarini tahlil qilish orqali ochib berilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada Ibratning "Tanlangan asarlar" to'plamida yozilgan "Haq so'z" maqolasi mohiyati sharhlangan. Shoirning "Qoziyi qotil" she'rini chuqur tahlil etilgan. Bundan tashqari turli adabiyotshunos olimlarning Ibratning huquqshunoslikka qo'shgan hissasi haqida bildirgan mulohazalaridan iqtiboslar keltirib, fikrlarini dalillab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: huquqshunoslik, huquqiy faoliyat, adolat, jamiyat, demokratiya, mulla, imom, masjid, qarz, mukofot, jazo, ta'lim, ilm.

He can not be denied that there were two types of judges working in the time of the incident. In the best case scenario, Ishkhan Tora Turakurgan and Khanabad completed the twenty-first term of the 20th century in the first quarter of the twenty-first century, when he tried to achieve good fate by addressing good issues and disputing issues that would be better. We have a lot of information about it, but sometimes we just have to think about it. Grandfather Nurillo Kori Abdullaev recalls that the October Revolution took place, and Russian-tactical schools were opened in our country. Some of the schoolchildren from the Bekabad-based home-school home-based home-based home-based school have just gone to study at Turakurgan's new boarding school. Twelve-year-old Muradilla's "fugitive" was expensive for her father. The priests tried to turn the boy into a "straight path" by not allowing the priests to enter the mosque.

"What is wrong with me," Said Holmirza-aka, whose faces approached the door of the mosque. "Muradilla is lying in the boarding school. I do not care if my bed is empty, I do not want to go back to my old school".

"It is forbidden for a father who does not have the strength to perform his child's namâz in the mosque's mosque," said the imam as if he were touching the sensitive area. People could do nothing but join the imam's opinion. In search of salvation, Khalqozi brother came to Ishaqkhan to Turre Ibrat in Turakurgan. In the hands of the governor, who had a high reputation among the rulers and the elders, he came to the neighborhood to clarify the issue.

“The Mosque is for God, the door of this gateway must always remain open to praying for all its servants! Ibrat Said firmly. - It is appropriate for the turmoil. It is unjust for a child to punish such a father. The government's opening of a boarding school is a kind of kindness to children. Do not stick to old attitudes. You will still see, many will want to teach their children there, to tell them about worldly knowledge. Our children need to study Arabic alphabet, Russian alphabet. Do not be ignorant, go on the path of enlightenment!

Ishaqkhan's decree, no clerk or imam, did not have the slightest objection to speaking against him. Hulk-zahir was given the opportunity to have him restrain the threshold of the mosque.

Muradilla Holguziev, a boarding student at that school, eventually came to Russia and continued to study. As a doctor of medical sciences, hundreds of doctors trained at the Samarkand State Medical Institute.

Ibrater scientist Ulugbek Dolimov, who lived and worked in Turakurgan at the beginning of the 1960s, collected the necessary information about the life and activities of the elderly, Ishakhan, who had written the following information: "Ishkhan was the most just, the most brave judge in the bar. He listened to both the rich and the poor, and sentenced them to judgment.

I do not know that he has been in the service of my ten-year-old for a while, and has never bribed him, and he has been riding on the rich, on the contrary, he tried to ease the difficulties of the poor. True, the corrupt judges brought the people, the upper class, the money, the various items. However, Ishachkhan would send the owner back with the owner. Therefore, the richest people decided to appoint Mamatkul Hoji, the deputy of the latter, instead of Ishaq. But they were silent. As a result, Mamatkul hoji was an enemy to Isaac by the end of his life. Ishak Khan worked as a judge only for the sake of the people. There were books on Russian jurisprudence at his home, his booth, and he was well aware of the Russian law and rules.”

Those who knew Ishaqkhan and who knew his stuff were always impressed with this perfect man. Even the description of his description was taken up by

contemporaries and leading intellectuals. Those texts are of utmost importance as they can give a true picture to the present generation. The article “The Right Word”, written in 1908 by Ibrat's “Selected Works” collection, was not accidentally entered. The article, written by the publisher of the other author, has been deliberately put in place as an appendix. The Kokand writer and poet Ibrahim Davron (1874-1922) wrote his article as a defender and advocate of the good: “At the Namangan treasury, Turakurgan Kazimi, as a sayyid-ul-haj Iskhak, is a true Muslim, knowing that some of his colleagues are perfect. A prominent advocate of the death of a prominent supporter, was surprised at the fact that he was a Hodja vos-vos. But we did not have any other way of thinking about the idea of the sentence and sentence of the sentence. Of course not. In Baku, Huseynzoda, a member of the opposition, was shocked by the idea. The Ishkhan Tora, meanwhile, also rejects the idea that it is permissible to deny it. For, a perfect person does not create disobedience, even if he dies as an atom of the infinite labor of the world and his enduring destiny”.

The article clarifies when surfing ends. The author warns that the Taukurkans can be deprived of such a fair judge by their actions and actions. “If the people of Turakurgan, who were dependent on Ishaqhan-Hakim, did not know human rights, they would be thrown into a pile of rubble, pestilence, madhouse, and crusade. I have been compelled to write honest and grueling comments on the civilian rights and interests of the walking. And it is worthy of note”.

Why, then, are the Russian authorities allowed to take control of the judiciary and the judiciary in the Muslim world? The question arises in our minds. "As it is known, after the occupation of Central Asia by Russia, the judiciary was preserved and the possibility of judicial proceedings on the basis of the Shariah rules was abandoned," commented Ulugbek Dolimov. "This is a showcase of" fair "and" self-sufficient "for the native people. But the prosecution of criminal cases of state significance was banned in the judiciary. The prizewinner was one of the sources of wealth in the upper class. The scoundrels, with the rich, were scarcely overcome by the people, diminished their lives, worked for the interests of the high class, and lived with bribery. "

Ibrat himself did not finish his poem "Qazi qotil":

*Outwardly one day people are ignorant,
Always indulgent.
To kill the feathered Eddy,
It would have been good to praise it.
He made a sudden mufsit qase,
Breastfeeding is a perverted justice.
Many people are sorry, so do you.
He always slaughtered his soul.*

It is clear that those who are guilty of wanton salvation will find that their bad conditions are tense. The fact that the life of this sort of sadness is explicitly explicitly stated in the Case of the Cossack Judge indicates that Ibrat's not only in his life, but in his creativity, is in full accuracy in proof and proof. It is no doubt that Ibrat, who holds fast the two demands, has served as a prerequisite for the elevation of justice in the rule of law.

In 1935, Iskhokhon Ibrat was removed from all positions and was forbidden to teach in schools. He was later arrested in 1937 for "anti-Soviet propaganda" and imprisoned. In April of the same year, he dies in a prison located in Andijan, he was then 75 years old. The burial place of Ishokhon Ibrat is still unknown.

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